

AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF CONSUMER TRUST AND SATISFACTION IN E- MARKETING CHANNELS IN DEHRADUN

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to empirically examine the relationship between consumer trust and satisfaction in e marketing channels within Dehradun district, Utrakhand.within the rapid growth of digital marketing and e commerce in India .understanding regional consumer perception has become crucial. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from 200 respondents who have previously used online shopping platform. The study analyzes the factors influencing consumer trust (such as website quality, security and perceived risk) and their subsequent impact on satisfaction and purchase intention. The findings reveal the consumer trust significantly affects satisfaction , which in turn influences future purchasing behavior .the study concludes that enhancing service quality ,transparency, and data security are key strategies for improving consumer trust and satisfaction in e marketing channels in semi urban area like Dehradun.

KEYWORDS: Consumer Trust, Consumer satisfaction, E marketing, marketing channels

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, electronic marketing has revolutionized the way business interacts with consumers. The increasing penetration of the internet, smart phones and digital payment system has made online platforms essential channels for marketing, communication and sales. The growing internet penetration and Smartphone usage in India, e marketing channels(online stores ,social media commerce ,mobile app) are increasingly important even in smaller cities like Dehradun.Consumers are now exposed to a vast array of online products and services and their purchasing behavior is heavily influenced by their trust and satisfaction with these e marketing channels. Consumer trust and satisfaction play a critical role in determining the success and

sustainability of e-marketing platform trust reduces the perceived risk associated with online transaction, while satisfaction reflects the overall evaluation of the consumer's experience .together they influence consumer's loyalty, repeat purchase decision and word of mouth (WOM) recommendations.

Dehradun as a rapidly developing city and a emerging digital hub in Uttarakhand , presents an interesting context for studying consumer behavior in e marketing . The city diverse consumer base ranging from students professionals to entrepreneurs offers valuable insights into how trust and satisfaction shape online purchasing decisions at the regional level.

This research aims to empirically examine the relationship between consumer trust and satisfaction in e marketing channels in Dehradun.it seeks to analyze the relationship between consumer trust and satisfaction in e marketing channels in Dehradun.it seeks to identify key factors influencing these dimensions, measure their interdependence, and provide recommendation for business to enhance customer engagement and loyalty through effective online marketing strategies. This study aims to fill the gap by focusing on Dehradun and empirically analyzing how attributes of e marketing channels affect trust and satisfaction.

LITRATURE REVIEW

The internet is mainly an open worldwide communication network. The increased availability of internet is influencing the growth of internet users around the world. The popularity of E commerce has been increased tremendously .Within the rise of digital channels, e marketing (online marketing via website, mobile apps , social media ,etc) has become critical for firms seeking to reach consumers . a systematic review the effectiveness of e marketing to strengthen the product quality customer trust and commitment with organizations by Maha Abbas Alazwari (2021)found that e marketing significantly enhances customer satisfaction and brand loyalty particularly when service quality , information and online interaction is strong. Another study the impact of e- service quality and customer on consumer behavior in online shopping focusing on e -service quality in online service quality influences customer behavior such as repurchase intension and word of mouth and that both loyalty and trust play role in this online context. Studying buying behavior and their motives and intension along with the attitude of the e- consumers is within the theoretical construct of the theory of reasoned action. The theory of reasoned action (Fishbein,1980), examine the relationship between attitude and future intension to participate in these buying behaviors. Which includes when they click on banner ads response to e mail advertisement, use of comparison engines attention and time to customer review and reaction towards them, product basket, online support services, use of email, feedback forms etc.

Cheung et al(online consumer behavior , a review and agenda for future research,2003), a model called MIAC which means a model of intention ,adaptation and continuance for the development of an online consumer behavior framework. This model predicts that basically behavior is governed by intention. Satisfied consumers are most likely to continue hence adaption and

continuance are connected with each other by several mediating and moderating factors such as trust and satisfaction .there are individual consumer characteristics, and online merchants and intermediaries characteristics which affect consumer buying behavior. Cultural factor is also considered as an important factor in both adopting and the success of E marketing. The main factor in the adoption of e marketing is the availability of supportive atmosphere and environment. In order for the E marketing tool (i.e the internet) to serve as an effective marketing tools ,all parties in the relationship or the transaction must be familiar with internet and appreciate the benefits and the potential applications of internet. Studies (Sharma & sheath ,2020;singh 2022)show that Indian consumers increasingly use digital channels due to affordability and accessibility of the internet, however lack of trust and inconsistent service quality remain challenges in smaller cities.

Conceptual framework: Fig: 1

Hypothesis

- H11: Website quality positively influences consumer trust in e marketing channels.
- H12: Perceived risk negatively influences consumer trust.
- H13 Consumer trust positively influences consumer satisfaction.
- H14 Consumer satisfaction positively influences purchase intention.

Objectives of the research

- To study the factors influencing consumer trust in e marketing channels.
- To examine the relationship between consumer trust and consumer satisfaction
- To analyze the impact of consumer satisfaction on future purchase intention.
- To provide recommendations for improving trust and satisfaction levels among e-marketing users.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive and empirical research design was used to understand relationship among variables through quantitative methods.

Population and Sample Size

Population of the study includes consumers residing in Dehradun district who have experience with e-marketing or online marketing. Sample size is 200. convenience sampling technique was used for sampling and well structured questionnaire using a 5 point likert scale was used.

Table: 1 Demographic profile of consumers

Demographic profile	Observation(n=200)
Gender	55% male 45% female
Age group	18-25 (50%) 26-35(30%) 36+(20%)
education	60 % graduate 40 % post graduate
Frequency of online purchase	70 % monthly , 20 % quarterly , 10 % rarely

FIG:2 Demographic profile of consumers

FIG: 3 Age group of consumer

FIG: 4 Education level of consumer

FIG;5 Frequency of online purchase

Key findings:

- Website quality and security has a positive correlation with consumer trust($r=0.68$, $p<0.01$).
 - Perceived risk showed a negative correlation with trust ($r=0.42$, $p<0.05$).
 - Consumer trust had a significant positive influence on satisfaction($B=0.61$, $p<0.01$)
 - Satisfaction also positively influenced future purchase intention($B=0.55$, $p<0.01$)
- Hence the entire four hypotheses were accepted.

DISCUSSION

The result indicates that consumers in Dehradun place high importance on website quality and secure payment system when engaging with e marketing platform. Consistent with prior studies, perceived risk negatively affects trust, while trust serves as a key driver of satisfaction. This implies that businesses operating in Dehradun must focus on improving transparency, ensuring data protection and maintaining service quality. Additionally digital literacy programs could further enhance trust among less tech savvy consumers

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concludes that consumer trust and satisfaction are independent and jointly influence the success of e marketing channels. Building trust through reliable service, prompt delivery and strong customer support significantly enhances consumer satisfaction and long term loyalty.

- Improve website quality and ensure secure payment system.
- Provide clear return and refund policies to reduce perceived risk.
- Enhance customer service responsiveness to build confidence.
- Conduct local digital awareness campaign to boost trust and participation.

LIMITATIONS

- This study is conducted in Dehradun district of Uttarakhand .limited to one district of Uttarakhand which may affect generalizability.
- Sample size is very small (200)
- Data collected via self reported questionnaire, may involve response bias.

FUTURE IMPLICATIONS

Future research could expand to other district of Uttarakhand or compare rural vs. urban perceptions. Longitudinal or mixed method studies can provide deeper insights into evolving consumer behavior in e marketing.

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